

Observation as a Local View: Why Measurement Looks Irreversible from Inside the System

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The origin question

Why does measurement appear irreversible, when the laws governing the systems we measure are reversible? This question sits underneath much of quantum information science and it kept surfacing in my own work before I had the language to state it cleanly. The microscopic dynamics of a closed quantum system are unitary which means information is only changed but never destroyed and the evolution can in principle be run backward. But the moment we observe a system, the description we are left with behaved as though information has been genuinely lost. I wanted to understand whether that loss is a fact about nature or a fact about our position relative to the system.

The scenario that prompted it

This question came to me as I imagined a scenario while studying measurement. For the scenario, imagine water held in a glass. To measure it, to read off what the system is, I have take away the glass, and in doing so the water spills across the floor. Nothing has been created or destroyed. The water that's supposed to be in the glass spilled on the floor because we took the glass away for measurement. The total amount of water conserved either way. But the act of measuring is itself what disperses the water, and the two situations it produces are not equivalent from the standpoint of someone describing them. To account for the water in the glass, I measure the glass. To account for the spilled water, I would now need to measure not only the water but its entanglement with the entire floor it has spread across. From the floor's perspective something has been added, and from the glass's perspective something has been lost. The asymmetry is not in the water, it is partly in what the observer can access and what they cannot and partly in the fact that observation itself is what made the dispersal.

This struck me as the everyday shadow of two precise statements in quantum theory, which the image holds together. First is that the act of measurement is not a passive reading but an intervention that disturbs the system by taking away the glass which spills the water. Second is that an observer who is then left with access to only part of a larger system, and who cannot jointly measure that part together with everything it has become correlated with, will necessarily describe an irreversible process, even though the global evolution (quantity of water) remains perfectly reversible. The first is about how the irreversibility is triggered and the second is about why it cannot be undone.

How I approached it

My first instinct was to ask the question in the terms of symmetry. The reversibility of the quantum mechanical evolution is itself a symmetry statement, under unitary evolution, certain quantities are conserved and the dynamics carry no preferred direction. So the puzzle

of measurement is really a puzzle about which of those conserved structures survive when I restrict my description to a part of the system, and which are washed out by the restriction. Asking this way, the question separates cleanly into two claims that are easy to conflate, whether information is actually destroyed, and whether if it is merely inaccessible to a particular observer. If its the former, irreversibility is fundamental. If its the latter, irreversibility is a feature of locality of access, not of the dynamics. To decide which reading the physics supports, I looked for where established theory already formalizes the move from a global, symmetric description to a partial, local one, because that is exactly the step my glass water floor intuition was performing informally and exactly the step at which a symmetry of the whole can fail to be a symmetry of the part.

What does existing research say

It helps to separate the two faces of the image, because established theory treats them as distinct mechanism that compound. The first is measurement *back-action*, in quantum mechanics one cannot extract information about a system without coupling to it and that coupling unavoidably disturbs it. Taking away the glass is not a neutral act of reading, it is the interaction that disperses the state (water). This is the active face, The observer's intervention is what triggers the irreversibility in the first place, rather than merely witnessing it.

The second face is what happens to the information once it has been dispersed, and standard quantum theory makes it explicit through *reduced density matrix*, when a system is entangled with an environment, the description available to an observer of the system alone is obtained by tracing out the environment. It is worth being accurate about why this single operation turns reversible dynamics into irreversible description. Unitary evolution writes the system's coherences, the off diagonal terms that encode its capacity to interfere into correlations shared between system and environment. The partial trace discards the environment, and with it every term that referenced those shared correlations and what remains is a state who's off-diagonal structure has been suppressed precisely to the extent that the system became entangled. Although no information has left the universe, the map from the global state to a local one is mapped many to one and distinct global states get sent to the same reduced state, so the operation cannot be inverted from local data alone. That non-invertibility is the irreversibility which is made formal. This is the passive face, even setting aside who or what triggered the dispersion, the conserved quantity the local description fails to preserve is exactly the coherence carried off into the correlations we can no longer reach.

The decoherence program developed by Zeh [1] and Zurek [2] shows that these two faces are not cleanly separable, because the action of dispersion or the role of observer can be taken by the environment unprompted. Through environment induced superselection [2], a system rapidly becomes correlated with an environment of overwhelmingly many degrees of freedom, which effectively 'measures' the system through its own internal interactions,

¹ "On the interpretation of measurement in quantum theory," *Foundations of Physics* **1**, 69–76 (1970)

² "Decoherence, einselection, and the quantum origins of the classical," *Reviews of Modern Physics* **75**(3), 715–775 (2003)

without requiring a deliberate observer on demand. Once those environmental records become mutually distinguishable, the system looks classical to any local observer and the correlations needed to reverse the process are spread across a reservoir no realistic measurement can gather back together. To explain the above sentence, records mean, the copy of information about the system which is stored in the environment. And these records are changing or influencing the environment in some way, and this change in environment is precisely what we target to check the decoherence of the original system. And by mutually distinguishable, it refers to the overlap of the environment due to system state. To explain this more clearly, let's take a system in superposition with fresh environment, $(\alpha|A\rangle + \beta|B\rangle) \otimes |E_0\rangle$. The interactions become, $\alpha|A\rangle|E_A\rangle + \beta|B\rangle|E_B\rangle$. Now to get the coherence of this system, it's the off-diagonal term in the system's reduced description and when we trace out the environment, that off-diagonal term comes out multiplied by exactly $\langle E_A|E_B\rangle$.

So, systems coherence = (original coherence) * $\langle E_A|E_B\rangle$.
 and the record's distinguishability = how small $\langle E_A|E_B\rangle$ is.

Going back to our original point, this is precisely the obstruction that is described, it is not that the joint information is gone, but that no accessible measurement can recover it.

Relational quantum mechanics, in Rovelli's formulation [3], sharpens the interpretive point. It treats the state of a system as defined relative to the observer interacting with it, rather than as an absolute, observer-independent fact. Under this reading, the irreversibility I was puzzled by is not a property the universe possesses on its own, but a property of a description tied to a particular vantage point, consistent with the view that asymmetry lives in the observer's access, not in the dynamics.

My inferences

Taken together, these frameworks support the second claim of my original question, while showing that the active and passive faces are two halves of one process. The apparent irreversibility of measurement is most coherently understood because of locality of access; the observer's intervention disperses the system's coherence into correlations with an environment, and the observer is then left describing the non-unitary information losing map not because information is destroyed but because they cannot access the global correlations into which it has dispersed. Stated in the language I started from, a symmetry of the closed system, the reversibility, and the conserved coherence that goes with it, simply is not a symmetry of the restricted local description, and the broken piece is precisely what the observer cannot reach. The water is conserved, what changes is the scope of what can be measured, and the act of measuring is itself part of what changes it.

This suggests a useful way of picturing observation itself as a kind of magnifying glass. The focal point, the present interaction, is sharply resolved, while everything correlated but

³ "Relational quantum mechanics," *International Journal of Theoretical Physics* **35**(8), 1637–1678 (1996)

inaccessible exists at the periphery, real but progressively smeared or blurred as the records that would resolve it disperse beyond reach.

I find the above framing productive because it is disciplined about its own limits. There is a claim we could work with, that the structure of what an observer can resolve constrains the irreversibility they will infer which is at least in part, expressible in terms of correlations, records and measurement statistics. We can also take a stronger interpretation, about whether the unresolved boundary (of the magnifying glass analogy) has a genuinely different status, which I do not believe any experiment I currently know how to formulate could settle. I think it's essential to mark that boundary clearly rather than let the intuition overreach, in keeping with how the decoherence and relational papers separate their testable content from their interpretations.

Possible future work

The question this leaves me with is whether the structure of information leakage can be exploited even without full access to the environment. If irreversibility is locality of access rather than true loss, then the way a system's coherence disperses into its correlations is not featureless noise, it has structure inherited from the coupling, and structure is something one can characterize and, in principle, partly compensate. Error mitigation techniques such as Probabilistic error cancellation already do something of this type by exploiting the statistical structure of how the two become correlated. This points to a direction I would like to pursue, whether the symmetries of a given encoding control how favorably that dispersal is structured. I suspect this could clarify exactly where the boundary between accessible and inaccessible information lies and how close to that boundary can one usefully operate.

References

- 1 H. D. Zeh "On the interpretation of measurement in quantum theory," *Foundations of Physics* **1**, 69–76 (1970)
- 2 W. H. Zurek "Decoherence, einselection, and the quantum origins of the classical," *Reviews of Modern Physics* **75**(3), 715–775 (2003)
- 3 C. Rovelli "Relational quantum mechanics," *International Journal of Theoretical Physics* **35**(8), 1637–1678 (1996)